

Another Facet of a Conducting Polymer : Dissolution and Redeposition of Polypyrrole

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A galvanostatic process of dissolution and redeposition has been developed using a chemically deposited polypyrrole on a cotton substrate as the positive electrode in trifluoroacetic acid. The redeposition of the conducting polymer has been carried out on metals like Pt or ITO (indium tin oxide) or Al. In this process, the conducting polymer is solubilised in the medium and transported to the cathode. The deposited polypyrrole has an excellent morphology for use in the conducting polymer battery. The infrared spectral features are analysed and compared with the parent polymer.

It has been very well demonstrated that organic conducting polymers are very viable electrode materials for secondary batteries¹⁻⁹. Polypyrrole is one such polymer, which has been synthesised from pyrrole by either electrochemical¹⁰⁻¹⁵ or chemical oxidation¹⁶⁻¹⁸; during these oxidations the film is formed on an inert substrate such as Pt or Au or optically transparent and electrically conducting glass. The properties of polypyrrole as an electrode material have been enunciated by several studies¹⁹⁻²⁵. The morphology of the polymer film has been probed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM)²⁶ and by scanning tunnelling microscopy²⁷.

We wish to report in this communication the anodic dissolution and cathodic redeposition of polypyrrole by galvanostatic polarisation on substrates such as Al and ITO (transparent indium tin oxide glass). In this galvanostatic experiment, polypyrrole is dissolved and transported through the medium to the cathode where it is deposited. The electrochemical properties of the cathodically deposited polypyrrole is compared with polypyrrole formed by anodic oxidation of pyrrole. This behaviour of polypyrrole establishes one other facet of the synthetic metal—namely dissolution and redeposition,

generally observed with most naturally occurring metals (M) in electrochemical baths. The morphology of the cathodically formed polymer film on Al or ITO has been examined by SEM. Furthermore, EDAX analysis of the cathodically deposited sample shows no trace of the supporting electrolyte metal ion (Al) in the polymer.

Results and Discussion

The galvanostatic electrolysis at polypyrrole (A) anode and Al cathode was conducted from 20 μ A to 1.00 mA; Fig. 1 shows the changes in cell emf as a function of time. The cell voltage increases slowly upto about 30 s and reaches a limiting value. After about 120 s the voltage shows a slow decline; this is attributed to the depletion of the polypyrrole on the anode. The depletion of the black conducting polypyrrole can also be visually seen at the anode during the galvanostatic electrolysis. At the cathode a slow growth of polypyrrole layer is observed during this electrolysis. Fig. 2 shows the SEM recording of the deposited film at the end of the galvanostatic electrolysis. The grain size variation is observed in these deposits: a big particle surrounded by smaller particles. The

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Fig. 1. A plot of impressed voltage vs time during the galvanostatic electrolysis of polypyrrole (A); anode : Cotton/PPY and cathode : Al; medium : 0.1 M TFA containing 0.1 M AlCl_3 .

grain size is evaluated by Cottrell's method²⁸ using the relationship,

$$L = \frac{l}{(P_L - 1)} \quad (3)$$

where P_L is the grain boundary per unit length which is related to the magnification and radius of the particle. The grain size of the particles is in the range of 0.5 to 1.17 μ . In the same figure the SEM of the anode is also shown before and after the galvanostatic electrolysis. The anode developed a large number of cracks during the electrolysis; under higher magnification of 5000 (Fig. 2) the polypyrrole depleted layer is observed by the darker region. The experiments conducted with polypyrrole gave a similar impressed voltage vs time curve as shown in Fig. 1. The EDAX of the cathodically deposited polypyrrole (A) shows no difference from the initial composition (the absence of Al from the supporting electrolyte).

The spectroelectrochemical experiment of galvanostatic electrolysis with ITO (indium tin oxide) as the cathode and polypyrrole (A) as the anode shows the appearance of a well defined broad absorption maximum in the region of 400 to 1000 nm. The optical density at 600 nm increases to 1.25 after passing a charge of 26.2 mC. The observed behavioural pattern during this electrolysis is shown in Fig. 3. The optical density at 600 nm region increases linearly with time as shown in Fig. 3A, indicating the process is proceeding smoothly.

Reversal electrolysis : The galvanostatic electrolysis was also conducted by reversing the polarity to examine the possibility of redepositing polypyrrole (A) on the anode. This process is observed only in situations when the original anode is not completely depleted of polypyrrole and films still having sufficient conductivity to maintain the flow of current. The increasing thickness of polypyrrole is visually observed in these experiments. Fig. 3A shows the optical density decreasing in the 400–1000 nm region due to the removal of polymer that has been deposited on the ITO.

Cyclic voltammetry of cathodically deposited polypyrrole : The cyclic voltammetric curve of the polypyrrole deposited by galvanostatic electrolysis has been recorded in aqueous and non-aqueous medium to compare its behavioural pattern with polypyrrole formed by electrochemical oxidation of pyrrole. The characteristic features are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. In the oxidised state of the polymer, the orientation of the dopant appears to have changed to bring about a significant shift in potential. The cathodically deposited polymer in 0.1 M TFA showed an anodic peak at about the same potential as the electrochemically formed polymer (at 0 V). However, the cathodic peak is displaced towards the negative potential (Figs. 4 and 5). Furthermore, the cathodically deposited film is stripped off at either negative (–0.80 V) or positive (1.0 V) potentials in comparison to the anodically deposited film; its adherence to the metal is poor. It may be noted that the medium does not contain any chloride ion to passivate Al.

The infrared spectral features of the polymer precipitated at the bottom of the reaction chamber during the chemical reaction, the polymer deposited on the Al cathode and the polymer on the Al substrate oxidised at 0 V vs SCE are given in Table I. These features are compared with already known features of polypyrrole in Table I. A cathodically deposited polymer is similar in characteristics to the anodically deposited polymer. It appears that hydroxylation of the polymer occurs as the peak around 3200 cm^{-1} is broad indicating the overlap of NH and OH bands. It has all the other features

Fig. 2. *Upper* : SEM recording of cathodically deposited PPY (A) on Al; magnification $\times 5000$.
Lower : SEM recording of cotton/PPY; magnification $\times 5000$.

Fig. 3A. *Upper* : Spectroelectrochemical study at ITO cathode and polypyrrole anode in TFA containing AlCl_3 ; the absorption increasing with time.

Lower : Reversal electrolysis; the absorption curve does not return to original even after 120 min (same duration as the deposition), thin film of polypyrrole remains on ITO.

of C=C stretch, ring stretch and C-N stretch. The band at $3\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears upon electrochemical oxidation of the polymer. Furthermore the observed features at other wavenumbers ($500\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are significantly different from the electrochemically formed polymer in perchlorate medium¹³ and is attributed to the PTS moiety, which has absorption maxima at $1\,200$, $1\,140$, 950 , 700 and 550 cm^{-1} . Thus it appears that the cathodically deposited polymer has the NH band.

The studies conducted here suggest that chemically

polymerised polypyrrole on cotton thread can be dissolved into the solvent such as TFA under anodic polarisation and redeposited at the cathode. The ir spectral data suggest that polypyrrole which has been deposited on the cotton fibre is in the neutral state as it has the $3\,400\text{--}3\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band. The PTS being surface-active it is likely to be adsorbed on the cotton fibre before the chemical deposition of the polymer. The galvanostatic oxidation produces the oxidised polymer in the soluble state. This migrates to the cathode and gets reduced to form again the neutral polymer on the surface. There

Fig. 3B. A plot of optical density (O.D.) vs time during in situ galvanostatic deposition of PPY on ITO; anode : cotton substrate/PPY; cathode : ITO; medium : 0.1 M TFA containing 0.1 M AlCl₃; current : 1.0 mA.

is likelihood of hydroxylation of the polymer taking place in this transfer. The overoxidised samples of polypyrrole exhibit this hydroxylation^{30,31}. The solubilisation mechanism of doped poly(phenylene sulphide) in the presence of a solvent has been discussed by Frommer²⁹. According to this interpretation the polymer dissolves if it is in intimate contact with the solvent; solvation of the reactive radical intermediates and dopant counterions. During

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of cathodically deposited PPY on Al; W.E. : Al/PPY (cathodic deposition); $i_0 = 2.4$ mA; A.E. : Pt-gauze; medium: 0.1 M TFA; $v = 20$ mV s⁻¹.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram of anodically deposited PPY on Pt; W.E. : Pt-gauze/PPY (redeposited); A.E. : Al-plate; $v = 0.20$ V s⁻¹; $Q = 1.13$ C; medium : 0.1 M TFA.

the galvanostatic electrolysis such as the one conducted here, the oxidation of the polymer to a positively charged state appears to attract the solvent molecule, facilitating solubilisation. This process may reduce the inter- or intrachain crosslinking in the polypyrrole which is rendering it originally insoluble.

The proposed mechanism involves

PPY and PTS represent polypyrrole and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid respectively, and ⌘ represents the cotton fibre on which PTS is absorbed. The process of dissolution of polypyrrole is indicative of its behaviour when a metal is oxidised into solution and redeposited at the other electrode. This deposition appears to result in structural rearrangement; as a result the cyclic voltammogram peak and the infrared spectral features are shifted with respect to the cathodically deposited polymer.

TABLE I—IR SPECTRAL FEATURES OF DIFFERENT SAMPLES OF POLYPYRROLE

Type of sample	V_{\max} cm^{-1}	Reference
Polypyrrole perchlorate	1 600, 1 490, 1 140 990, 800, 620	30
Neutral polypyrrole	3 380, 3 150, 1 600 1 480, 1 280, 1 120 1 002, 960, 650	30
Electro-polymerised polypyrrole (with no pyridine)	3 440, 2 000, 1 576 1 461, 1 304, 1 195, 1 043, 608	31
(with pyridine added to the medium)	3 416, 2 000, 1 576, 1 461, 1 304, 1 195, 1 043, 608	31
Ferricyanide polymerised polypyrrole (with no pyridine in the medium)	3 416 (broad), 1 576, 1 461, 1 304, 1 195, 1 043, 608	31
(with added pyridine)	3 458 (broad), 2 080, 1 630, 1 576, 1 461, 1 304, 1 195, 1 043, 608	31
Overoxidised polypyrrole	3 699, 3 593, 3 160 (broad), 3 110, 2 340, 2 274, 2 239, 1 725, 1 539, 1 397, 1 244, 1 200, 1 100	32
	1 800, 1 610, 1 380, 1 250 1 065, 680 1 514, 1 307	33
Anodically deposited polypyrrole in TFA	3 431, 2 937, 1 553, 1 446 1 180, 1 002, 978, 797 617, 553, 431	Present work
Cathodically deposited polypyrrole in TFA	3 200 (broad), 1 650, 1 390, 1 200, 1 140, 950, 720, 550	Present work
Cathodically deposited polypyrrole oxidised at 0 V for 22 h in TFA	1 630, 1 400, 1 200 1 120, 560	Present work

Experimental

Pyrrrole (Riedel) was distilled and the fraction boiling at 120° was collected and stored in a dark-colored bottle. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (Aldrich) and trichloroacetic acid (TCA) (Thomas Baker), AlCl_3 (SDS Chemicals), $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (Sarabai Chemicals), *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (Koch-Light), tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (Southwestern Analytical Chemicals, Austin) were used in the

preparation of solutions. Al (99.99%) (Precious Metals Co.) and indium tin oxide (ITO) glass (CNRS, Meudon) were cleaned with acetone (AnalaR) before the experiments.

The cyclic voltammetric recordings were done using a PAR 273 potentiostat/galvanostat in conjunction with an Omniograph (Houston Instruments) X-Y recorder. The power supply (Dynamlog Micro Systems, U.S.A.) of 22.5 V with a provision for obtaining intermediate voltages provided the required current for the experiments.

A JEOL JSM 840 scanning electron microscope was used for recording the polypyrrole deposited samples. EDAX analysis was also performed on the same samples. In situ spectroelectrochemical experiments were performed using a Shimadzu, UV-160 with a microcomputer controlled double-beam recording spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the anode : The chemical deposition of polypyrrole (A) was carried out in a beaker containing pyrrole (0.01 M), $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (0.01 M) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.8 g) in trifluoroacetic acid at 22° . A cotton thread (twine) of high purity was washed well with distilled water and was dropped inside the beaker. The reaction was carried out for 23.5 h. At the end of this period the thread was deep black; it was taken out with tongs, washed well with distilled water and subjected to natural drying. The polypyrrole obtained here is designated as polypyrrole (A). A similar procedure was adopted for depositing polypyrrole in trichloroacetic acid. (This polymer is designated in the present work as polypyrrole (B)). The SEM of the polymer on cotton thread showed a high degree of smoothness. The conductivities of the samples were measured by four-probe method and in the range $15\text{--}20$ ($\Omega \text{ cm}$) $^{-1}$. The precipitated solid in the bath was pressed into pellets and it showed a similar conductivity³.

Preparation of cathode : Al (5.5 cm \times 0.90 cm) was treated with dilute acid for 5 min, then buffed for 15 min and cleaned in trichloroethylene and later with acetone (AnalaR).

The electrodes were mounted on a perspex rectangular sheet (1.40 cm \times 4.8 cm) containing a

tapped hole through which a brass screw could be fitted and tightened. The electrodes were mounted using these screws. The copper wire from the galvanostat was connected to the cotton thread through an aluminium foil wound round it and pressed rigidly under high pressure or through sputtered gold of a few micron thickness on one end of the thread. The electrodes were placed in the electrolytic cell containing $AlCl_3$ solution. In all the measurements the connecting leads were kept above the solution by about 3 cm; in other words, the connecting points were not in the solution. In the galvanostatic experiments the cathode and anode areas were 4.95 cm^2 ($5.5 \text{ cm} \times 0.90 \text{ cm}$) and 0.86 cm^2 . The electrodes were separated by about 1.0 cm. The Al cathode was washed well with distilled water and acetone (AnalaR) after electrodeposition for taking it for further analysis. For spectroelectrochemical recordings, the cathode used was ITO, which was fitted into 1 cm path-length cell. The anode was kept out of the path of the light beam.

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